

temperature for 24 h, and then filtered and recrystallised from alcohol.

3-(p-Diazobenzoyl-N β -arylidinohydrazone)indoles (4): Compound 2 (0.01 mol) in dilute HCl was diazotised at 0° with NaNO₂ and then added slowly to a solution of indole (0.01 mol) in dilute KOH (10%) containing crushed ice. The resulting red solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Sl. no.	Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	146	65
2.	3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	144	64
3.	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃	124	69
4.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₃	142	71
5.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃	158	68
6.	CH=CH-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃	103	64
7.	3,4(O-CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	167	66
8.	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄	97	65
9.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₃	154	67
10.	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₃	151	69
11.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ O ₃	147	64
12.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ O ₃	158	68
13.	5-Br-2-OH-C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ BrN ₅ O ₃	150	70
14.	5-Br-4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ BrN ₅ O ₄	126	65
15.	5-I-4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ IN ₅ O ₄	144	67

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Pharmacological screening: The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Representative compounds were screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v).

Out of 15 compounds, 8 compounds were found to be active against *S. aureus* and 7 compounds active against *E. coli*, and 5 compounds active against both the species. Compounds having 4-methoxyphenyl, 4-methylphenyl, 3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl and 4-chlorophenyl substitutions were found active against both the species.

Out of 8 compounds screened, 3 compounds were effective at both the concentrations (35 and 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). Two compounds were found effective only at higher concentration. Compounds having 2-hydroxyphenyl, 2-chlorophenyl and 5-bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl substitutions were found effective at both the concentrations.

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Synthesis of some Aminoacetamide Derivatives

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IN continuation of our work on acetamide derivatives¹, we have synthesised some 1(*H*)-4-(*N'*-arylaminoacetamido)-5-carbethoxy-pyrimidin-2-ones (3) with a view to get better therapeutic agents. 5-Carbethoxycytosine (1) prepared by the reported method², was chloroacetylated with chloroacetylchloride in benzene to get 4-*N*-chloroacetyl-5-carbethoxycytosine (2), which on condensation with various aromatic amines yielded compound 3 (Scheme 1).

The structures of 1-3 were supported by elemental analysis and ir spectra. The ir spectrum of 1 showed characteristic bands and 3 450 (NH for free NH₂) and 3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH for pyrimidine ring). The peak at 3 450 cm⁻¹ disappeared and a new peak appeared at 1 640 cm⁻¹ (C=O for CONH) in the ir spectra of compound 2. Moreover, compounds 1-3 gave characteristic bands at 1 560 (C=C), 1 630 (C=N), 3 300 (NH), 1 690 (C=O cyclic), 1 300 (C-N) and 1 730 cm⁻¹ (for ester carbonyl), supporting structures of the compounds.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the synthesised compounds was checked on tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

Scheme 1

4-N-Chloroacetyl-5-carbethoxycytosine (2): A mixture of 5-carbethoxycytosine (0.1 mol) and chloroacetylchloride (0.15 mol) in dry benzene (200 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. On evaporation of the solvent, the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from benzene, (73%, 19.0 g), m.p. 241° (Found: N, 16.15. C₉H₁₀ClN₃O₄ requires: N, 16.21%).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	177	67
2.	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	186	71
3.	3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	196	70
4.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	201	66
5.	4-OC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	192	68
6.	2,3-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	207	60
7.	2,6-(CH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	211	64
8.	5-CH ₃ -2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	195-96	43
9.	2-Cl-4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	201	60
10.	2-CH ₃ -4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	197	71
11.	2-Cl-4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	211	62
12.	2,5-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	164	62
13.	2,6-(Cl) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	181	68
14.	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄	159	63
15.	4-NH ₂ -SO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	268d	67

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

1(H)-4-(N'-Arylaminoacetamido)-5-carbethoxypyrimidin-2-ones (3): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and appropriate aromatic amine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30-40 ml) was refluxed for 3 h in the presence of K₂CO₃ (2-3 g). The contents were

then poured into cold water and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Pharmacological screening: The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using cup-plate⁸ method. Representative compounds were screened for anti-tubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₈₇R₀) by the absolute concentration method⁴.

Results and Discussion

Antibacterial activity: Out of 15 compounds (3), 8 compounds (sl. nos. 1, 4, 5, 7-9, 12, 15) were found to be active against *S. aureus* and 7 compounds (sl. nos. 3, 4, 6, 7, 12, 13, 15) active against *E. coli*. Compounds having 4-methoxy, 2,6-dimethyl, 2,5-dichloro and 4-sulphonamido substitutions were found to be active against both the species (sl. nos. 4, 7, 12, 15) (Table 1).

Antitubercular activity: Out of 7 compounds (3) screened (sl. nos. 2, 4, 7, 10, 11, 13, 15; Table 1) none was found effective at lower concentration (35 µg ml⁻¹). But only compound sl. no. 13 having 4-methoxy substituent was found active at higher concentration (100 µg ml⁻¹).

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Studies on Biologically Active Heterocycles. Part-IV. Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of some 2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazolo/thiadiazolo[3,2-a]-s-triazine-7-thiones

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MANY *s*-triazine derivatives have a wide variety of uses such as pesticidal, herbicidal, antifungal and antibacterial activities^{1,2}. On the other hand, the importance of 1,3,4-oxa/thiadiazole derivatives as biologically active compounds are

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